

ISoRD 2014

**Design Guidance for Robust Design
using Load-Strength and
Design of Experiments.**

by

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Robustness

- the degree to which a system or component can function correctly in the presence of invalid inputs or stressful environment conditions (IEEE).

Nokia's CEO

I want you to:

- **Be more creative**
- **Take more risk**
- **Work faster**
- **Work cheaper**
- **And reduce Warranty costs 50%**

Tools at the bottom of the V:

- **Design Review (IEC 61160)**
- **FMECA (IEC 60812)**
- **FTA (IEC 61025)**
- **DOE**
- **FEM simulation**
- **Tolerance analysis**
- **Load-Strength analysis**
- **Degree of freedom analysis**
- **Monte Carlo simulation**

HOBBS CLATTERING: HB1C.HM 10/13/2004
Time = 0

Taguchi

Signal (S) – the design parameters

Noise (N)– use and environment

Optimize S/N ratio

Measured in dB

The Test Result of an L16 Taguchi Experiment

Performance →

Optimum:
A2,G1,I2,J1,K1,O1

Only level 1
is shown!

Signal – Noise
ratio in Db →

Only level 1 is shown i.e. A1, B1, C1...O1

$$R = \int_0^{\infty} f_s(S) \left[\int_0^S f_L(L) dL \right] dS$$

$$R + F = 1$$

Can be solved using for example Weibull++ software

For a power transistor Weibull distributed
Strength $\beta=1.2$ and $1,8$ and Load $\beta=1.4$ and 3.1 have
been observed

Standard Dev. For S-L: $S_{S-L} = \sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}$

Safety Margin:

$$SM = \frac{\bar{S} - \bar{L}}{\sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}}$$

SM	Prob. of failure, F
2.326	10^{-2}
3.090	10^{-3}
3.719	10^{-4}
4.265	10^{-5}
4.753	10^{-6}

$$LR = \frac{S_L}{\sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}}$$

Case A

LR = 0

Case B

LR = 1

performance shall be specified at end of lifetime

The designer must take degradation into account

Log failure rate

$$SM = \frac{\bar{S} - \bar{L}}{\sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}}$$

$$LR = \frac{S_L}{\sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}}$$

**A.D.S. Carter:
Failure rate as
Function of SM**

$$SM = \frac{\bar{S} - \bar{L}}{\sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}}$$

$$LR = \frac{S_L}{\sqrt{S_S^2 + S_L^2}}$$

Addition of tolerances for sum and differences:

$$R = ax + by + cz + \dots$$

$$S_R = \sqrt{(a \times S_x)^2 + (b \times S_y)^2 + (c \times S_z)^2 + \dots}$$

Addition of tolerances for logarithmic equations:

$$R = k \times x^\alpha \times y^\beta \times z^\gamma \times \dots$$

$$\frac{S_R}{R} = \sqrt{\left(\alpha \times \frac{S_x}{x}\right)^2 + \left(\beta \times \frac{S_y}{y}\right)^2 + \left(\gamma \times \frac{S_z}{z}\right)^2 + \dots}$$

$$S_{eff} = 16S - 15F = 16 \times 2.3 - 15 \times 0.3 = 32.3 Nmm$$

$$\bar{S} = 2.3N$$

$$\bar{A} = 16 \times 2.3 = 36.8 Nmm \quad \bar{B} = 15 \times 0.3 = 4.5 Nmm$$

$$S_S = 0.03N$$

$$\frac{S_A}{A} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{S_S}{S}\right)^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.03}{2.3}\right)^2} = 0.0130 \quad \frac{S_B}{B} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{S_F}{F}\right)^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.075}{0.3}\right)^2} = 0.250$$

$$\bar{F} = 0.3N$$

$$S_F = 0.075N \quad S_A = 0.0130 \times 36.8 = 0.480 \quad S_B = 0.250 \times 4.5 = 1.1250$$

$$S_S(eff) = \sqrt{(S_A^2 + S_B^2)} = \sqrt{(0.480^2 + 1.1250^2)} = 1.2231$$

$$\bar{L} = 0.4N$$

$$S_L = 0.07N$$

$$\bar{L}_{eff} = 54 \times 0.4 = 21.6Nmm$$

$$\frac{S_{L(eff)}}{L_{eff}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{S_L}{\bar{L}}\right)^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{0.07}{0.4}\right)^2} = 0.1750$$

$$\bar{S}_{eff} = 32.3Nmm$$

$$S_S(eff) = 1.2231Nmm \quad S_{L(eff)} = 0.1750 \times 21.6 = 3.78Nmm$$

$$SM = \frac{\bar{S}_{eff} - \bar{L}_{eff}}{\left(S_{S(eff)}^2 + S_{L(eff)}^2\right)^{0.5}} = \frac{32.3 - 21.6}{\left(1.2231^2 + 3.78^2\right)^{0.5}} = 2.6932$$

From a table of Gauss distribution we find: R=99.64 or F=0.36% failures

Flexible snap-lock

Fixed stop

Airbus A 380 test wing breaks just below load target

After fatigue testing the wing was loaded until failure

The failure occurred between 1.45 and 1.5 times the limit load

This is within 3% of the 1.5 target

Wing deflection of 7.4m (24.3 ft) was recorded

FEM had shown that the A380's wing had "No margin at ultimate load" To save weight they 'played the game'

The result was delay of the program !

Load – Strength simulation of plastic mouldings

Ref.: Valter Loll: "Load-Strength simulation of Plastic Mouldings"
 QRE Int. Vol. 4 pp. 223-226 (1988)

Figure 4. Simulation of design with safety factor $n = 1.2$ orientation 90° to optimum

Figure 5. Simulation of design with safety factor $n = 2$ and joint, unreinforced material

Figure 6. Simulation of design with safety factor $n = 10$ and joint, reinforced material

Conclusion:

- TAAF is obsolete
- Robustness to be designed in
- DOE and S/N ratio useful
- Tolerances by DOE/Loss Function and partial derivatives
- Design guidance based on DOE and simulation
- Load-Strength analysis-
More research on L and S distributions and SM/LR curves

Thank you for your attention

Questions ?